

Government Strategies for Addressing Environmental Security Impacts of Dolomite Mining in Oreke, Kwara states

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Abstract

Dolomite mining plays an important role in Nigeria's economic and industrial development, but it also brings severe environmental risks to the communities where it takes place. In Nigeria, dolomite mining is an important economic activity which supports the metallurgy, construction, manufacturing, and agricultural sectors. Yet, mining in communities like Oreke in Kwara State has raised serious environmental concerns, including air and water pollution, loss of biodiversity, land degradation and health hazards. Environmental security, which involves the protection of human communities and the ecosystem from environmental harm, is therefore a compelling issue. This study explores government strategies for addressing the environmental impacts of dolomite mining in Oreke. Using a mixed-method approach that included questionnaires, in-depth interviews, key informant interviews, and non-participant observations, data were gathered from 61 participants, comprising government officials, transporters, artisans, miners, farmers, and local inhabitants. The results indicate that regulations and technical strategies, such as environmental laws, regular inspections, enforcement of mining standards, environmental impact assessments, and stakeholder engagement, exist to improve environmental security. Nonetheless, discrepancies persist between policy implementation and actual practices, especially regarding site reclamation, consistency in enforcement, control of illegal mining activities, and public awareness of compensation schemes. Additionally, there was a noted lack of synergy with civil society and minimal community involvement. The research concludes that enhanced enforcement, clear communication, active participation from the community, and effective post-mining rehabilitation are essential for sustainable environmental management in Oreke and comparable mining communities.

Keywords: Government Strategies, Environmental Security, Dolomite Mining

INTRODUCTION

The interaction between human society and the natural environment has remained a cardinal factor in the security, survival, and development of civilizations globally. Human societies rely on the utilisation of natural resources to satisfy economic, social, and technological demands, and this connection has become more pronounced with industrialisation and the increase in population. According to Seymour (2016), the security, protection, and development of human society are driven by sustained interactions between man and the environment, while Jack et al. (2016) emphasise that humanity's capacity to develop tools and social systems determines how natural resources are utilised for growth and survival. As global demand for minerals increases, resource extraction has become a major driver of economic development, particularly in developing economies, but this has also heightened environmental risks and security concerns.

Globally, mining contributes greatly to the advancement of industries, the growth of infrastructure, and the creation of jobs. Minerals like limestone and dolomite play essential roles in construction, metallurgy, agriculture, and manufacturing sectors. Nevertheless, the advantages of mining are often offset by significant environmental and social repercussions, particularly in areas near mining operations. The processes involved in mineral extraction and processing generally result in land degradation, deforestation, biodiversity loss, air and water contamination, and changes to the landscape (Sutrisno & Azhari, 2020). Dust emissions from blasting, crushing, and transportation of minerals reduce the quality of air and pose severe respiratory health risks, while the release of heavy metals and particulate matter pollutes soil and water bodies, undermining food security and agricultural productivity (Kumar, 2014; Olatunji et al., 2017).

These environmental challenges directly threaten environmental security, which broadly refers to the protection of the human population and ecosystems from environmental degradation, pollution, and resource depletion that undermine public health, livelihoods, and abiding sustainability (Ojo, 2018). In mining dependent communities around the world, environmental insecurity displays through declining agricultural yields, displacement of populations, water scarcity,

increased disease burden, and social instability. As environmental conditions degenerate, susceptible communities become more exposed to poverty and livelihood loss, reinforcing cycles of insecurity and underdevelopment.

In many developing regions, especially in Africa, natural resource exploitation remains a key pathway for economic growth and poverty reduction. Governments across the continent have promoted mining as a means of generating revenue, creating employment and attracting foreign investment. However, limited institutional capacity, weak regulatory frameworks, and inadequate enforcement mechanisms often undermine environmental security efforts. Consequently, mining-related environmental degradation continues to cause potent issues to environmental security and sustainable development across the region (Oruonye & Ahmed, 2020). Communities hosting mining operations frequently suffer more environmental issues with respect to the economic benefits from these operations.

In Nigeria, the exploitation of solid minerals has increasingly gained attention as part of efforts to diversify the economy from the dependence on crude oil. The country is endowed with a wide range of mineral resources, including limestone, dolomite, coal, gold, and bitumen. Solid minerals such as limestone and dolomite play crucial roles in supporting industries like agriculture, cement production, construction, and manufacturing. Scholars such as Adekoya (2003) and Obaje (2009) note that the mining sector holds significant potential for contributing to employment generation, national development, and revenue growth if properly managed.

Dolomite, a carbonate mineral composed of calcium magnesium carbonate ($\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$), is explicitly valuable due to its wide industrial applications. Despite its economic significance, dolomite mining is associated with considerable environmental challenges. The processes involved blasting, crushing, grinding, and transportation which generate dust, noise, and waste materials that degrade land, reduce air quality, and pollute water sources. These impacts pose serious challenges to environmental security and public health, particularly in rural communities where livelihoods depend heavily on farming and access to clean water. Recognising these risks, the Nigerian government has established institutional, legal, and policy frameworks aimed at regulating mining activities and minimising their environmental implications. The Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act of 2007 serves as the main legal framework governing mineral exploration and exploitation in the country. Its provisions cover environmental protection, mine closure, land reclamation, and compensation for affected communities. This Act is supported by the National Environmental (Mining and Processing of Coal, Ores and Industrial Minerals) Regulations of 2009, the Nigerian Minerals and Mining Regulations of 2011, and the National Environmental (Quarrying and Blasting Operations) Regulations of 2013 which set standards for occupational health and safety, pollution control, and environmental management in mining operations.

Additionally, the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Act mandates that all mining projects go through environmental assessment prior to commencement. The EIA process is designed to forecast and identify potential environmental and social impacts and propose mitigation measures before casualty occurs. Regulatory agencies such as the Ministry of Mines and Solid Development (MMSS), the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA), and federal and state ministries of environment are tasked with enforcing these regulations and ensuring compliance with environmental standards (Babalola, 2013). Despite these frameworks, environmental degradation related with mining still persists in many parts of Nigeria, bringing up concerns about the effectiveness of government interventions.

The Oreke community, known for one of Nigeria's prominent dolomite reserves, illustrates the intricate connection between economic advantages and environmental security issues related to mining activities. For many years, dolomite extraction has taken place in Oreke, leading to increased job creation, revenue generation, and the provision of raw materials for various industries (Akande & Agbalajobi, 2013). Nonetheless, these advantages have come with considerable environmental drawbacks. Farmlands have been degraded, surface and groundwater sources contaminated, and natural landscapes altered by continuous mining activities. Residents have also reported increased respiratory health problems linked to dust emissions from blasting and crushing operations.

The livelihoods of residents in Oreke, who largely rely on agriculture and access to clean water, are increasingly jeopardized by these environmental issues. Concerns such as air pollution, water contamination, loss of biodiversity, land degradation, noise pollution, and decreasing agricultural productivity pose significant threats to environmental security and sustainable development within the community. Comparable trends have been observed in other mining

regions throughout Nigeria (Ako et al., 2014; Eludoyin, 2017; Merem et al., 2017), yet there is still a lack of empirical research on how government actions specifically tackle the environmental security effects of dolomite mining at the local level.

Despite having regulatory and institutional frameworks in place, the effective security of the environment in mining communities like Oreke is hindered by weak enforcement, restricted monitoring capabilities, lack of technical expertise, and poor cooperation among regulatory bodies (Oruonye & Ahmed, 2020). Informal and small-scale mining operations often function outside formal regulatory structures which worsens environmental degradation. Residents frequently express concerns over insufficient consultation, limited information access, and insufficient compensation for environmental damage, which diminishes trust in government institutions and increases social tensions.

In this context, this study examines government measures in addressing the impact of dolomite mining on environmental security in Oreke community. By assessing the regulatory frameworks, the roles of various institutions, enforcement strategies, and technical solutions, this study aims to assess how effective government actions have been in addressing environmental degradation. The anticipated results are intended to enhance policy discussions by pinpointing implementation gaps and proposing ways to improve environmental security and encourage more sustainable dolomite mining practices in Oreke and comparable mining communities.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the government strategies used addressing the environmental security impacts of dolomite mining in Oreke community and to proffer plausible recommendations. The main objectives are to

1. Examine the regulatory strategies used by government in addressing the environmental security impacts of dolomite mining in Oreke community, and
2. Evaluate the other extant technical strategies used by government in mitigating environmental security impacts of dolomite mining in Oreke community.

Significance of Study

Environmental Security is vital to the protection of the inhabitants of Kwara State. Therefore, this study intends to address the gaps in the existing literature on government strategies for addressing environmental security impact in the study area. The findings generated from this study will provide valuable recommendations to relevant governmental, non-governmental authorities and organisations in developing suitable policies that are appropriate for the improvement of the mining sector and addressing the impact of mining on environmental security. This study will also serve as an essential source of information for policy makers and civil society organisations in managing mining operations for sustainable development in Nigeria. It is anticipated that this study would provide a useful guide for future research in this area of focus and other related areas.

Scope of Study

The study focuses on government strategies in addressing environmental security impact of dolomite mining in Oreke community in Ifelodun Local Government Areas in Kwara State of Nigeria. This study covers the period of 1985 to 2025. This period was chosen because it covered the duration that dolomite mining entered full capacity production in these communities to the present mining operations which tends to have adverse effect on environmental security. This time frame will help in investigating how dolomite mining has impacted the security of the environment due to unregulated and unrestricted mining operations with a view to proffering recommendations to regulate mining and the attributed negative impacts.

Study Area

Source: NESREA Kwara Field Office ICT Unit and Administrative map of Kwara State, 2025

Figure 1: Map of Study Area

Oreke is located on latitude N008.48759⁰ and longitude E005.20301⁰ with an elevation of 278m in Ifelodun Local Government Area of Kwara State, Nigeria. It has a tropical wet and dry or savanna climate with an average yearly temperature of 29.79°C. Dolomite mining exists in Oreke, Kwara State, specifically within the Ifelodun Area and Ire district. The marble site is located about 4.5km southeast of Oreke, with an access road leading towards Oreke Ore Ago road. Oreke marble is strictly dolomitic, and the deposit covers up to 7 cadastral units. Dolomite mining, particularly in the Oreke region within Ifelodun Local Government Area of Kwara State, is a significant activity.

Government Measures in Addressing the Impact of Dolomite Mining in Nigeria

There have been several studies conducted on the impact of mining in Nigeria (Adeniyi et al. 2013; Ako et al., 2014; Merem et al., 2017; Ojo, 2020; Odoh et al., 2024). However, few studies have documented government measures in addressing the impact of mining in Nigeria (Igwe, 2011; Olalekan et al., 2016; Omotehinse & Ako, 2019). For instance, Olalekan et al., (2016) explained that although Nigeria is richly endowed with a variety of solid and industrial minerals, the mining of solid and industrial minerals contribute very little to the national economy. In 2024, the mining and quarrying sector accounted for 7.68% to Nigeria's overall National GDP in the first quarter of 2024 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2024). In the light of the rising challenges associated with Nigeria's petroleum sector, the government of Nigeria increased its focus on the solid and Industrial minerals sector as a potential catalyst for the economic development (Sanusi, 2010). In fact, some stakeholders in the Nigerian mining industry have indicated that the sharp drop in the oil price has been a blessing in disguise. They argue that it provides a well-needed incentive to diversify the economy (Michael, 2019). Official publications similarly establish that the government wishes to develop the solid and industrial minerals sector to diversify the economy by increasing its contribution to the country's GDP, exports and foreign reserve (Ministry of Mines and Steel Development, 2016).

Nigeria's first attempt at regulating mining was the 1946 Act, and it included environmental protection, but this has not changed the mining-induced environmental degradation (Omotehinse & Ako, 2019). According to surveys conducted by Nigerian governments over the last few decades, the tin mines [lethal pits] of Jos with around 1,500 dangerous mining ponds have devastated the physical landscape of the terrain (Goki et al., 2016; Omotehinse & Ako, 2019). Also, the coal mines in Enugu have been partially converted into refuse dumps (Omotehinse & Ako, 2019). In view of the new Nigerian Mining and Minerals Act (NMMA) of 2007, Section 4.6.1, it is essential that mining grantees obtain consent from local authorities prior to the commencement of the development of mineral title (Naibbi & Chindo, 2020).

Olatunbosun et al. (2013) in their studies revealed that the Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act 2007 ("the Act") was passed into law on March 16, 2007 to repeal and replace the Minerals and Mining Act, No. 34 of 1999 for the purposes of regulating the exploration and exploitation of solid materials in Nigeria. Adeoye (2010) posited that this Act is

aimed at making the sector more competitive. The 2007 Act established the federal government's ownership of all mineral resources, the offices in charge of overseeing the mining sector, the procedures for acquiring the rights to search for and produce mineral resources, and the rights and obligations of holders of mineral titles (defined as a Reconnaissance Permit, an Exploration License, a Small-Scale Mining Lease, a Mining Lease, a Quarry License and a Water Use Permit) (Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act, 2007). Provisions such as tax holidays of three to five years and exemption from payment of customs and import duties for mining equipment are included as incentives for investors. Also, the creation of the Solid Minerals Development Fund (SMDF), a fund tasked with catalysing growth in the mining sector is introduced (Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act, 2007). The corresponding 2011 Regulations further established procedures by stipulating the duties of each government office charged with mining sector oversight, the application procedure for would-beholders of mineral licenses, and the royalties, fees, rents and compensation payable by holders of mineral titles (Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act, 2011).

Ite et al. (2016) also identified that the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency Act was established in 2007 (NESREA). This Act was charged with the responsibility of protecting and developing the environment in Nigeria, as well as enforcing all environmental laws, regulations, standards, policies, guidelines and conventions on the environment to which Nigeria is a signatory. The Agency has powers to prohibit processes and use of equipment or technology that undermine environmental quality, conduct field follow-up of compliance with set standards and take procedures prescribed by law against any violator, subject to the provision of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999, and in collaboration with relevant judicial authorities establish mobile courts to expeditiously dispense cases of violation of environmental regulation. Concerning the protection of the environment, Adefulu (2010) noted that the Act prohibits pollution of water course, alterations in water supply and provides that everyone who uses water in connection with mining operation shall ensure that the water in use does not contain injurious substances in quantities likely to prove detrimental to animal or vegetable life.

Akpan (2020) in his work *Ownership and Control of Natural Resources in Nigeria: Rumor vs. Reality* revealed that the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps (Amendment) Act 2007 is also an institutional framework to prevent illegal mining. This law establishes that the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC) among other functions is to provide protection, crisis resolution and the protection of public infrastructure at the federal, state and local levels nation-wide (Vanguardngr, 2015). The Civil Defence Corps has the following responsibilities of ensuring continuous surveillance of infrastructures, sites, and projects belonging to the federal, state, and local governments; entering and searching premises and confiscating any materials believed to be used for vandalism or suspected proceeds of vandalism; having the authority to make arrests with or without a warrant; detaining, investigating, and initiating legal action against any individual suspected of committing an offense under this Act; providing the Ministry with intelligence information on issues related to crime control in general, as well as subversive activities by members of the public intended to undermine any government program or policy (Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps Act, 2007).

The Nigerian government views dolomite mining as important to economic diversification, infrastructure development, and job creation. It has recognised dolomite as a key mineral and encourages its extraction as part of Nigeria's Mining Roadmap (Ministry of Mines and Steel Development, 2023). Additionally, it has created legal structures, including the Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act (2007) and the National Environmental (Mining and Process of Coal, Ore and Industrial Minerals) Regulation (2009), to manage mining operations and draw in investment. It also has synergy with the United Nations Industrial Development Organisation (UNIDO) that supports sustainable mining practices of dolomite extraction, by encouraging environmentally sound technologies and local value addition. UNIDO emphasises the integration of small-scale miners into formal systems and promotes mineral-based industrialisation that aligns with Sustainable Development Goals (United Nation Industrial Development Organisation, 2020). Furthermore, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) has advocated for policies that align resource extraction with ecological sustainability, calling on nations to implement cleaner technologies and enforce stringent environmental regulations in mining. It highlights the importance of comprehensive environmental impact assessments (EIAs), the protection of biodiversity, and the restoration of ecosystems (United Nations Environmental Program, 2022). As noted by NESREA (2021), the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) serves as the primary environmental authority in Nigeria, empowered to uphold environmental regulations within the mining industry. NESREA mandates that mining companies carry out EIAs and submit Environmental Management Plans (EMPs) prior to starting their operations. The agency has also flagged non-compliance issues in dolomite mining zones and emphasised the need for environmental accountability.

From the above literature, it is clear that the government's regulatory measure for managing environmental security and socio-economic effects of mining has succeeded a little bit in suppressing the problems of loss of vegetation cover, mass destruction of water bodies, loss of biodiversity, land-use changes and food insecurity, increased social vices and conflicts, high cost of living, and pollution which causes severe havoc on the environment, people and government but has not brought about the expected result. The reviewed literature also showed that the measures taken mostly failed to check environmental security and socio-economic effect of mining in the communities. There are also cases of accusation of backing of illegal miners by important people in government (Kolawole, 2019), thereby making it difficult for the illegal miners to be brought to book even when they are caught.

However, these studies have not made effective recommendations about how these government regulatory measures can be made more effective to manage environmental security of mining. In the light of this, it is hoped that this study contributes to the existing studies by making plausible recommendation on how the government can successfully make the regulatory measures effective in addressing environmental security of dolomite mining.

Theoretical Framework

The Environmental Regulations Theory came to prominence from the Conference of Human Environment organised by the United Nations in Stockholm in 1972 (Wang, 2016). The theory focuses on the need for environmental protection and regulation. It refers to the set of principles and guidelines that govern the interaction between human activities and the natural environment. This theory aims to promote sustainable development and environmental protection by regulating human activities that harm the environment. It was developed in response to the necessity for a framework that could guide the regulation of anthropogenic activities to protect the environment (Barnett, 2001). Since then, the theory has evolved and has been applied in various contexts.

The Environmental Regulations Theory has been criticised to be ineffective in some contexts such as weak institutions and lack of enforcement mechanisms in some countries. It also has issues of high cost of implementation of environmental regulations which can discourage some countries from adopting the international agreed environmental regulation. In the same vein, the limited technical and financial resources make it very complex and difficult to implement. Similarly, some critics argue that the theory puts too much emphasis on command and control regulations, which can be inflexible (Singha, 2018).

In its strength, Environmental Regulation Theory provides a robust framework for ensuring environmental security in dolomite mining by establishing legal and institutional mechanisms to mitigate the negative ecological impacts of mineral exploitation. According to Ramanathan (2023) the theory presumes that when regulatory frameworks are properly designed and enforced, facilities will be compelled to internalise environmental costs, thereby promoting sustainable development. For dolomite mining, which often involves deforestation, dust emissions, habitat disruption, and groundwater contamination, environmental regulation will be critical for preserving ecological balance and protecting local communities. In addition, Environmental Regulation Theory aligns with the concept of environmental security by emphasising risk prevention and resilience building in mining communities. By enforcing buffer zones, regulating blasting activities, and managing chemical application can mitigate issues associated with environmental threats and promote the abiding health of local ecosystems (Bruch et al., 2007). In dolomite mining, where open-pit methods and the use of heavy machinery are common, such regulatory interventions are essential for minimising landscape degradation and ensuring that exploitation does not undermine community livelihoods or biodiversity.

The utilisation of the environmental regulation theory is to evaluate government's strategies of addressing environmental security impacts of dolomite mining in Oreke community in Kwara State.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research methodology adopted for the study. The methodology provides a coherent framework for achieving the study's objectives. The study employed an integrated research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitatively, descriptive survey research designs was applied, while the qualitative component utilised an exploratory design (Adeniran, 2019). This combination enabled a comprehensive understanding of government's strategies of addressing environmental security impacts of dolomite mining in Oreke community in Kwara State. The quantitative aspect relied on questionnaires. Consistent with Goundar (2012), quantitative research is suited for phenomena measurable by numerical values. The qualitative component consisted of In-depth Interviews (IDIs), Key Informant Interviews (KIIs), Non- Participant Observation and secondary materials including reports, journal articles, and books which examine phenomena based on quality rather than quantity. A

mixed design was considered appropriate because it integrates the strengths of both methods, drawing on deductive and inductive reasoning to produce complementary and more reliable findings. The study focused on Oreke Community in Ifelodun Local Government Area of Kwara State. There were no authenticated and approved population by either National Bureau of Statistics or National Population Commission for Oreke community so an estimated population of Ifelodun LGA from National Population Commission in City Population (2022) was utilised. The sample size of the study was determined using Sample Z-Score at 95% confidence level, 5% marginal error and 50% population proportion. The computed sample size was approximately 64. The study adopted purposive and random sampling to administer the questionnaire. However, 61 out of the 64 questionnaire distributed physically and online were retrieved.

For the qualitative component, purposive sampling was used to select participants. Additionally, interviews were conducted with National Environmental Standards and Regulation Enforcement Agency (NESREA), Environmental Consultants, Federal Ministry of Mines and Solid Development (FMMSD), Federal Ministry of Environment (FOE), Kwara State Ministry of Industry and Solid Mineral Development (KWMISMD), Kwara State Ministry of Environment (KWMOE), Kwara State Environment Protection Agency (KWEPA), Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC), Directorate of State Security (DSS), Nigerian Police Force (NPF), Farmers, Miners, transporters, artisans and well informed individuals.

Data were obtained from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data were generated through questionnaires, KIIs, IDIs, and Non Participant Observations which offered firsthand insights into the environmental security conditions from dolomite mining. Secondary data were derived from textbooks, academic journals, newspapers, official bulletins, online databases, and institutional reports. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained. Interviews were recorded and transcribed to complement the questionnaire findings. The questionnaires, both open and closed-ended, were designed in line with the research objectives and distributed.

Descriptive statistics including frequencies and percentages were used to analyse the questionnaire data. Qualitative data from KIIs, IDIs and Non Participant Observation were examined through contextual interpretation and thematic analysis. Secondary materials were used to triangulate and validate findings. The study encountered challenges such as difficulties securing some of the participants because of the conflict in the community from kidnappers, delays in retrieving questionnaires, and some non-responses. However, online questionnaire was transmitted to the community group to add to the physical ones collected. Additionally, organising and presenting data from multiple sources was time-consuming.

RESULT

Result from data generated from the study is discussed in this section. The data generated from the questionnaire, non-participant observation, In-depth interview, and key informant interview were administered on respondents in the study area in-line with the objectives of the study. The study was carried out on field survey to assess respondents view on government's strategies of addressing environmental security impacts of dolomite mining in Oreke community, Kwara State. A total of sixty four (64) questionnaires were administered on respondents, out of which sixty one (61) were retrieved. Therefore, the analysis of this study is based on the number retrieved and the responses from the non-participant observation, in-depth interview, and key informant interviews.

Regulatory strategies used by government in addressing the environmental security impacts of dolomite mining in Oreke community.

The regulatory strategies in which government mitigate the impacts of dolomite mining on environmental security in Oreke community is generated in this section. Data derived from the questionnaire, KII, IDI and Non participant observations were analysed respectively. The perception of the respondents on regulatory strategies in which government mitigate the impacts of dolomite mining on environmental security in Oreke community is presented on table 1.

Table 1: Perception of Respondents on Regulatory Strategies of Government in Addressing Environmental Security Impact of Dolomite Mining in Oreke Community.

S/N	Questionnaire items	Respondents Frequencies and Percentages %					TOTAL
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Not Sure	Agree	Strongly Agree	
i.	The government has enacted adequate regulations and policies to regulate dolomite mining activities	0 (0%)	8 (13.1%)	0 (0%)	43 (70.5%)	10 (16.4%)	61 (100%)
Ii	Regulatory Agencies strictly enforce mining regulations and impose penalties on violators	4 (6.5%)	11 (18.0%)	2 (3.3%)	35 (57.4%)	9 (14.8%)	61 (100%)
Iii	Land reclamation and rehabilitation are mandatory components of government mining regulations	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	8 (13.1%)	38 (62.3%)	15 (24.6%)	61 (100%)

Source: Author’s analysis 2025

Analysis in this section as shown on table1 revealed the perception of the respondents on the regulatory strategies of government in addressing the environmental security impacts of dolomite mining in Oreke community. From table 1, it could be deduced that government has enacted adequate regulations and policies to regulate dolomite mining activities. 11 (18.0%) of the respondents disagree, 43 (70.5%) agreed while 10 (16.4%) strongly agreed to this perspective. This was complemented by NESREA, FMMSD, and NSCDC. They stated that they have regulations that oversees mining activities. Some of the respondents also stated that security personnel from the NPF, DSS, NSCDS and FMMSD mostly regulate mining and blasting activities in the mining sites. Also from the table, 4 (6.5%) strongly disagree, 11 (18.0%) disagree, 2 (3.3%) not sure while 35 (57.4%) and 9 (14.8%) agree and strongly agree that Regulatory Agencies strictly enforce mining regulations and impose penalties on violators. According to NESREA respondent, the Agency gazette National Environmental Regulations on (Quarrying and Blasting Operation) and (Mining and Process of Coal, Ore and Industrial Minerals) and also organises stakeholders meeting. A respondent from the NPF informed that they normally assist and give security to Agencies like NESREA when they intend to impose penalties on violators.

The table also shows that land reclamation and rehabilitation are mandatory components of government mining regulations. 8 (13.1%) of the respondents are not sure, 38 (62.3%) agreed, while 15 (24.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed to this perspective. From respondents, it was observed that NESREA and FMMSD are responsible to ensure that there is reclamation and rehabilitation of the mining site after mining. It was observed with respect to the mining sites that implementation of this regulation was not active as some of the mining sites were left in gullies and abandoned. Most response from the miners with respect to the degradation and abandonment of site was that they are not through with mining in the site and will still go back to the site. Some respondents suggested that there is need for a reliable communication between the miners and the government to enhance effective rehabilitation and reclamation of the mining site after utilised. Similarly, the respondent from KWMISMD talked about their strategies to enhance the reclamation, proper profiling of miners and enforcement of community development agreement. Also, one of the environmental consultants explained that there is need for miners to submit environmental protection and rehabilitation plan to ensure the security of the environment.

Other technical strategies used by government in improving environmental security on dolomite mining in Oreke community.

This section presents the other technical strategies used by government in improving environmental security on dolomite mining in Oreke community is generated in this section. Data derived from the questionnaire, KII, IDI and Non participant observations were analysed respectively. The perception of the respondents on other technical strategies used by government in improving environmental security on dolomite mining in Oreke community is presented on table 2.

From table 2 below, data generated shows that Government Agencies regularly monitor dolomite mining operations. 10 (16.4%) of the respondents disagreed to this perspective, 6 (9.8%) are not sure while 36 (59%) and 9 (14.8%) agreed and strongly agreed to this perspective. According to the respondent from NESREA, they carry out routine

inspections and compliance monitoring inspections on the mining sites in Oreke. Some of the respondents from DSS, NSCDC, and FMMSD, they always participate during blasting operations in the mining site and routinely monitor the mining operation. Also, a respondent from NSCDC informed that they normally carry out general information visit, complaint visits and regular patrol within the mining sites. This helps them to adequately monitor the site and ensure that transported stones are licenced to prevent and mitigate illegal mining. The respondent from FMMSD explained that the level of monitoring has also mitigated illegal mining in Oreke community. He stated that at a time the Ministry compelled all miners to form cooperative and register for licence for easy identification in which the head of Oreke community was involved to ensure active cooperation.

The table also indicates that Government compel mining facilities to conduct environmental impact assessment (EIA) before mining begins. From the table, 5 (8.2%) of the respondents disagreed, 4 (6.6%) are not sure, 36 (59%) agreed while 16 (26.2%) of the respondents strongly agree to this perspective. According to the respondent from the FMOE, their ministry is responsible to ensure that all developmental projects carry out environmental impact assessment. He stated that the responsibility shifts to one of its Agency, NESREA to enforce compliance to facilities that fail to carry out EIA. In the same vein, respondent from NESREA explained that when the facility fails to carry out EIA, they are violated and asked to pay a violation fee to the federal government after which they are asked they are compelled to carry out environmental audit. He stated that violation to this directive and notification leads to sanction.

Table 2: Perception of Respondents on other technical strategies of government in improving environmental security on dolomite mining in Oreke community

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Respondents Frequencies and Percentages %					TOTAL
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Not Sure	Agree	Strongly Agree	
i.	Government Agencies regularly monitor dolomite mining operations	0 (0%)	10 (16.4%)	6 (9.8%)	36 (59%)	9 (14.8%)	61 (100%)
ii	Government compel mining facilities to conduct environmental impact assessment (EIA) before mining begins	0 (0%)	5 (8.2%)	4 (6.6%)	36 (59%)	16 (26.2%)	61 (100%)
iii	Government ensures that local communities are consulted before granting mining permit	0 (0%)	2 (3.3%)	15 (24.6%)	32 (52.4%)	12 (19.7%)	61 (100%)
Iv	There are government programmes that compensate or support communities affected by dolomite mining	0 (0%)	4 (6.6%)	34 (55.7%)	19 (31.1%)	4 (6.6%)	61 (100%)
V	The government conducts sensitisation and awareness campaigns on environmental impact of dolomite mining	0 (0%)	4 (6.6%)	16 (26.2%)	35 (57.4%)	6 (9.8%)	61 (100%)
Vi	The government promotes inclusive benefits for vulnerable groups in the mining affected areas	0 (0%)	4 (6.6%)	26 (42.6%)	25 (41%)	6 (9.8%)	61 (100%)
Vii	The government works effectively with CSOs, researchers and the communities in managing dolomite mining impacts	0 (0%)	6 (9.8%)	28 (45.9%)	23 (37.7%)	4 (6.6%)	61 (100%)

Source: Author's analysis 2025

The table above indicates that Government ensures that local communities are consulted before granting mining permit. 2 (3.3%) of the respondents disagree to this perception, 15 (24.6%) are not sure, 32 (52.4%) agreed while 12 (19.7%) strongly agreed to the perception. According to the respondent from FMMSD, before licence is given to the miner, an exploration form is been given to be return with an approval and consent from the community. When the form is returned, FMMSD investigates the reliability of the consent before giving mining approval to the mining

facility. In the same vein, a respondent from NSCDC informed that some miners use the exploratory permit to carry out mining operation without returning consent from the community to start mining but it is been notice they are stopped and arrested.

The table also shows that 4 (6.6%) respondents disagreed that there are government programmes that compensate or support communities affected by dolomite mining, 34 (55.7%) are not sure, 19 (31.1%) agreed, while 4 (6.6%) strongly agreed to this perception. The table shows that most people do not know if there are government programmes that compensate or support communities affected by dolomite mining. Also, the table 2 indicates that government conducts sensitisation and awareness campaigns on environmental impact of dolomite mining. 4 (6.6%) disagreed, 16 (26.2%) not sure, while 35 (57.4%) and 6 (9.8%) agreed and strongly agreed to this perspective. According to the respondent from NESREA, the Agency routinely carry out sensitisation and environmental awareness creation meeting with the Oreke miners association to educate them on the environmental implications of dolomite mining. One on the environmental consultants also informed that the miners and the community are being informed on the environmental consequences of dolomite mining. A respondent from the community also said that government normally carry out sensitisation on mining in Oreke. Similarly, one of the respondents also suggested that a body like NESREA green corps should be instituted in all mining communities like Oreke for regular advice and communication to the inhabitants.

Furthermore, data generated from table 2 indicates that the government promotes inclusive benefits for vulnerable groups in the mining affected areas. The table shows that 4 (6.6%) of the respondents disagreed to this perception, 26 (42.6%) are not sure, 25 (41%) agreed while 6 (9.8%) strongly agreed to this perspective. The table also indicated that 6 (9.8%) of the respondents disagreed that government works effectively with CSOs, researchers and the communities in managing dolomite mining impacts, 28 (45.9%) are not sure, 23 (37.7%) agreed, while 4 (6.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed to this perspective. However, more respondents are not sure of government relationship with Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) and researcher with respect to management of dolomite mining impact but those who agreed to this perception are close to those who do not have idea.

DISCUSSION

The findings show government deliberate efforts to manage the environmental security challenges associated with dolomite mining in Oreke community through various regulatory and technical measures. Most respondents recognised that there are mining laws and policies in place, with agencies such as NESREA, FMMSD, NSCDC, NPF and DSS working together to regulate activities, enhance compliance monitoring, enforce compliance and provide security at mining sites. The presence of enhancement of penalties, routine inspections, and stakeholder engagements advocates that the government is actively involved in environmental management.

However, the study also highlights gaps between policy and practice. Although regulations require land reclamation and rehabilitation after mining, observations from the field indicate that many sites are still left degraded or abandoned. This points to weaknesses in enforcement and follow-up. In the same way, even though environmental impact assessments are mandatory and generally enforced, some illegal mining activities continue, despite being reduced through closer monitoring and the registration of miners' cooperatives. Also Barkemeyer et al. (2015) in their study observed that the regulatory measures of government have failed to address environmental security and socio-economic effect of mining in Nigeria because it does not lend itself to the standards of international best practices.

While respondents largely agreed that communities are consulted before mining licences are issued, many were unsure about the existence of compensation schemes or special support for affected and vulnerable groups. Agbedion and Iyayi (2007) demonstrated that although policies such as Environmental Impact Assessment Act and the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency Act exist, inefficient implementation and limited community involvement obstruct effective outcome. This uncertainty suggests poor communication or limited visibility of such programmes. Despite the ongoing awareness initiatives, particularly from NESREA, the partnership with civil society organisations and researchers is still lacking. In general, the results indicate that enhanced communication, greater community engagement, and more reliable enforcement are essential for enhancing environmental security in the Oreke community.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study indicates that the government has taken significant steps to address the environmental security challenges linked to dolomite mining in the Oreke community. By implementing regulations, fostering collaboration among agencies, and conducting regular monitoring, the incidence of illegal mining has decreased, and oversight has been enhanced. Nevertheless, there remains a notable disparity between the promises of policies and the actual situations on the ground. Numerous mining sites still lack reclamation, enforcement is at times uneven, and post-mining rehabilitation is frequently overlooked. Moreover, many individuals in the community are not informed about compensation options, and there is limited interaction with civil society. To resolve these issues, stronger enforcement, clearer communication, increased community participation, and a firm dedication to adequate land restoration will be necessary.

It is recommended that

- NESREA, FMMSD and other government organisations should strengthen regulatory enforcement by ensuring strict compliance with mining laws, environmental regulations, penalties and rehabilitation requirements,
- Other technical strategies should be enhanced through regular monitoring, improved community engagement, stronger inter-agency coordination, effective EIAs, and transparent communication to ensure sustainable environmental security outcomes.

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